

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP.
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

Summary Work Session - II
Co-creation
Implementation Guidelines
One Health EJP

Grant Agreement number 773830

Date	8 & 9 October 2019
Venue	London
Meeting	Developing Implementation Guidelines – session II

(From left to right: Malin Jonsson, Charlotte Cook, Frits Vlaanderen, Sandra Cavaco, Cecilia Mia Wolff, Solveig Jore, Marieke Timmer, Kitty Maassen, Frank Koenen, Ines Mogami, Elina Lahti, Robert Dewar, Karin Nyberg, Annemarie Kaesbohrer, Victor Del Rio Vilas and Maria Noremark)

Participants	Email-address
Solveig Jore, Norway	solveig.jore@fhi.no
Malin Jonsson, Norway	malin.jonsson@vetinst.no
Cecilia Mia Wolff, Norway	cecilia.mia.wolff@vetinst.no
Charlotte Cook, The United Kingdom	charlotte.cook@apha.gov.uk
Robert Dewar, The United Kingdom	robert.dewar@apha.gov.uk
Marieke Timmer, The Netherlands	marieke.timmer@rivm.nl
Sandra Cavaco, Portugal	sandra.cavaco@iniav.pt
Victor Del Rio Vilas, The United Kingdom	vdelriovilas@yahoo.co.uk
Kitty Maassen, The Netherlands	kitty.maassen@rivm.nl
Marieke Timmer, The Netherlands	marieke.timmer@rivm.nl
Margreet te Wierik, The Netherlands	margreet.te.wierik@rivm.nl
Ines Mogami, The Netherlands	ines.mogami@rivm.nl
Frits Vlaanderen, The Netherlands	frits.vlaanderen@rivm.nl
Annemarie Kaesbohrer, Germany	annemarie.kaesbohrer@vetmeduni.ac.at
Frank Koenen, Belgium	frank.koenen@sciensano.be
Elina Lahti, Sweden	elina.lahti@sva.se
Karin Nyberg, Sweden	karin.nyberg@slv.se

This document is a summary of the session held in London on 08th and 09th of October at APHA, the United Kingdom (thank you Charlotte Cook and Robert Dewar for the organization). Presentations and flip overs will be shared via the members part of the COHESIVE website.

Programme:

Tuesday 09th of October

Morning 9.00h-12.30h:

- Introduction by Kitty Maassen
- 6 short presentations of the different activities (10 minutes per presentation, discussions included)
- Work session part 1: 'Advising Mike', make a description of the activity including the importance/goal, using the documents provided

Lunch 12.30h-13.30h

Afternoon 13.30h-18.00h:

- Work session part 2: 'Advising Mike', make a checklist of the possible terms of references for each activity

Wednesday 10th of October

Morning 9.00h-12.30h:

- Feedback round Tuesday 09th of October
- Work session part 3: What should your ideal One Health structure look like?
- Discussing collaboration with

Morning 12.30h-13.00h:

- Closure and dividing tasks

Lunch 13.00h-14.00h

Afternoon 14.00h-18.00h: Workpackage 3.1 led by Maria

Summary

Tuesday 08th of October

The session started with a welcome word from Kitty Maassen. Kitty Maassen explained the preliminary results from the sessions in Uppsala in April 2019 and from Brussel in July 2019 . The aim of the session was to further co-create the implementation guidelines for a One Health Risk Analysis System (OHRAS)¹. OHRAS is referred as:

Organized collaboration between food, medical and veterinarian professionals with respect to: signaling, risk assessment, response and control of (emerging) zoonoses at the national level (COHESIVE, 2019).

After the introduction, six short presentations were given on each activity of a OHRAS followed by a short discussion (see documents on activities):

- 1) Signalling by Sandra Cavaco
- 2) Joint Risk Assessment by Frank Koenen
- 3) Joint Risk Management by Frits Vlaanderen (written by Elina Lathi, Karin Nyberg and Frits Vlaanderen)
- 4) Feasibility Assessment by Kitty Maassen
- 5) Governance by Ines Mogami
- 6) Risk Communication by Kitty Maassen (written by Solveig Jore)

Topic: Discussing the activities

- 1) After the presentations, Kitty Maassen and Marieke Timmer introduced the assignment. The exercise for the session was to give advice to 'Mike' who is a One Health coordinator with a background in veterinary studies, working for a public health institution and got the assignment to build a OHRAS in his own country. The aim for at the end of the entire session was to be able to give advice to 'Mike' on the first steps how to approach this. The aim of the first part was to discuss the six activities in groups on the elements: description and the goals/importance. The groups were divided and after lunch, the results of the discussions were discussed plenary. Risk Communication

Topic: Discussing terms of references

In the afternoon, terms of references were discussed for each activity. Everybody could walk around and write on each flip over what they thought were 1) required elements and 2) optional elements in relation to what should/can be agreed upon per activity. After this, a discussion was held per activity on the elements and everybody could choose what elements should be classified as 'required' elements – with red stickers, 'optional' elements – with blue stickers and if there were people who thought that all elements should be included – these were indicated with yellow stickers. In addition, smileys were put to indicate elements that are liked (to prevent double elements). The idea (still open for suggestions and not decided yet) behind this was that the implementation guidelines will be presented in the form of a website or interactive pdf. These can have several layers. The most important elements can be at a higher level than the less important/optional ones. The activities that were discussed were: Signalling, Joint Risk Assessment, Joint Risk Management, Feasibility Assessment, Governance, Risk Communication. Due to

¹ It was jointly decided to use the word 'system' for this session.

time constraints Governance and Risk communication were not discussed. For the results, please kindly see the attachment below this document).

Wednesday 09th of October
Morning WP 2.1

Topic: Feedback

The day started with a brief feedback session on the day before. Everybody could express their thought by drawing their 'weather condition'. Most drawings had a sunshine and some clouds. Representing: that most of the participants thought that the morning session about describing the activities (including goals/important) went well, because of clear instructions and that the activity was done in groups were seen as useful. The afternoon session on the terms of references were seen as useful, but too long and less clear about the outcome. The main conclusions were that the participants did see that steps are taken to create the European OHRAS implementation guidelines, but would like to better understand how future sessions will add value to the bigger picture of WP 2.1 COHESIVE (in which phase are we in creating the implementation guidelines). A time schedule will be shared at the next COHESIVE meeting in Rome.

Topic: Building own structure

The idea is that after agreeing upon the needed activities that in a 'One Health risk analysis system (OHRAS)' the activities should be organized. However, the way to organize these is dependent on what kind of structures already exist etc. So, there are many possibilities and it is up to the countries to decide upon it. Kitty showed in her presentation several possibilities (governance over the whole system or per activity, signalling and risk assessment in the same group or separated). The exercise was to draft your ideal OHRAS with your own country in mind. Next, comments could be placed at the drawings and they were discussed in smaller (stand up) groups. Interesting was that many people put governance over the whole system. One of the needs expressed was how to deal with local specific challenges in an overall European implementation guideline

Topic: Collaboration FAO/WHO/OIE

Potential collaboration with the FAO/WHO/OIE (the tripartite) were discussed. The general idea was that it is good to collaborate, but main conclusions were that more information is needed in order to make the decision whether to collaborate or not. Currently, the FAO/WHO/OIE would like to receive support in evaluating different tools (they will have a session in 18-22 November in Rome). Potential advantages mentioned were that with the collaboration the reach will be bigger and increase the sustainability of the guidelines. However, if we decide to collaborate, participants indicated that it will be important to make clear that our implementation guidelines will focus on the European region. The discussion ended with the conclusion that it will be important to understand what support the tripartite would like to receive, think about how we can support the tripartite and what this collaboration can mean for us. Kitty will make an appointment to get a better understanding about the potential collaboration.

Topic: Abstracts

In relation to COHESIVE, there could be opportunities to send in abstracts as a group to different future conferences. Some participants indicated their interests in this. Cecilia Mia Wolff and Ines Mogami will think about a potential topic of an abstract for the 4th International Conference on Animal Health Surveillance in May 2020 in Denmark (ICAHS) (the deadline is extended to 10 November). Other abstracts and potential publications will be discussed in future meetings.

Others

A proposal was made to make the implementation guidelines as the Strategic Research Agenda for the One Health European Joint Programme published in July 2019.² The advantages of this type of publication is that it is interactive and online available. However, this type of publication is more difficult to print and might be costly. The type of publication for the guidelines has not been decided yet and will be discussed in future meetings. Another option is an interactive website. The disadvantage is that it is not printable.

****Main action points**:**

- Per activity: the description, importance/goals and terms of references will be written in groups by 14th of November (send to COHESIVE@rivm.nl – cc Kitty, Frits and Ines).
- The COHESIVE team from the RIVM will make a Word doc Version of what has been written on the flip overs.
- Organize the next meeting in Rome (Solveig, Rob, Cecilia, Annemarie and Frank will help).
- Cecilia and Ines will work on the abstract for ICAHS.
- Kitty will make an appointment with the Tripartite. Robert and Ines will support in thinking about how to collaborate.

Afternoon WP 3.1

Maria Noremark welcomed everybody and explained the recent updates. Per country, each person indicated what and how many interviews were done, what the main challenges were and what the next steps are. The number of interviews varied between 1 to 6 per country. Interviews were done with e.g. people from both veterinary and public health institutes and policy makers working for ministries at national level. Some of the participants indicated that recruiting people for the interview was relatively easy, while others found it hard. For example, in the United Kingdom recruiting e.g. policy makers was a challenge. Potential reasons for this mentioned were that they are relatively hard to reach and may not find this topic a priority. Possibly using people higher in hierarchy or with certain influence to invite them. Most of the participants experienced the interviews as very insightful and enjoyed doing them. Some of the participants are still in the process of doing interviews while others are transcribing and analysing first thematic topics. The next steps will be to transcribe and analyse thematic themes at national level and international level. The idea is to do the analysis part during the next COHESIVE meeting in Rome. Potential publication journals were discussed to publish (e.g. Eurosurveillance and One Health Outlook Biomedcentral). Also a list of authors and co-authors were listed.

****Main action points**:**

- Finish doing the interviews, transcribing them and make first steps to analyse themes (if possible).
- New co-authors will coordinate how to support with national participants.

² <https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/One-Health-EJP-Strategic-Research-Agenda.pdf>

Attachment

Signal

Description

- Information that might lead to action
 - Sign. break baseline
Surveillance system
 - Observation
- Information from active/passive/personal
 - Broader information sources from all sectors

Goal

- Evaluate situation for timely detection of an event (is this a real signal?)

Why?

- Minimise consequences for One Health

Signal – Terms of Reference

- Arrange documentation of signals/minutes
- Participants: from all relevant disciplines, think of Public Health, food, animal health, entomologist, ecologist, (depending on the goal) Determine responsibilities/tasks of the participants, chair, secretary etc...
- Regular meetings to discuss signals
- Consider: participants of expertise/experience with overview/certain mandate
- Determine process how to bring in signals
- Knowledge about 'baselines' for certain diseases, determine outbreak etc..
- Ad hoc meeting in case of an event (describe process/criteria when)
- Determine guidelines/checklist criteria when the signal should be further investigated/assessed (social unrest, new pathogen in your countr, unknown effect for public health etc...)
- Define where possible a platform to triage signals from different sources + tools to be established and continuously improved; common understanding of the process to be developed and communicated
- Define data ownership and privacy
- Sharing signals/information goes above individual publications (process)
- Consider: options for dissemination. Newsletter to professionals, escalate -> risk communication, outbreak management team etc..
- Confidentiality is the norm to 'broadcast'. A signal a shared/joined decision
- Med/Vet/Biological knowledge when analyzing/interpreting signals to evaluate the signal further on. Not only data scientists.
- Consider: 'Stable' group

Joint Risk Assessment

Description

- One Health risk analyses what might happen to humans, animals and/or the environment. How likely is it to happen, what are the potential consequences and estimate the level of risk

Goal

- Find out whether action is necessary to eliminate or reduce risk of the hazard for One Health

Joint Risk Assessment – Terms of Reference

- Maintain a list of experts on pathogen/ on industry that are familiar with JRA process. Put teams together as required. Flexible group or standing group for certain topics
- Participants respect each other's expertise and seek help when moving outside expertise. Determine roles/responsibilities
- Use of an JRA template + scoring scheme. Define your process (which tools, when)
- Ensure/coordinate access to data schemes across sectors for purpose of JRA
- Establish selection between RA – RM – FA. Set scope of JRA team
- Set out clear (otherwise ask for refinement) risk question and agree upon it
- Establish a group of not initially involved who can provide feedback and comments = quality check or review
- Determine whom to address the question
- Determine how the group is established – multidisciplinary

Joint Risk Management

Description

- Coordinated decision making and actions to respond to the risk

Goal

- Eliminate/mitigate or reduce risk for humans, animals and the environment or of the consequences at risk

Importance

- Best available outcome

Joint Risk Management – Terms of Reference

- Participants from relevant sectors/organisations with decision making mandate
- Transparent process in the decision
- Knowledge from the relevant sectors involved
- Specific group or ad hoc group and regular meetings?
- Determine what overrides/overrules in case of an impasse PH>VH or VH>PH
- Creating trust/relation by knowing each other. Example of Norway (+NL) Communication sharing information

Coordinated Risk Communication

Description

- Communications (in event) inside (to align outside communication) and outside system
 - 2-way
 - Established relationships system stakeholders
 - Tailored to risk groups
 - Perception of target groups

Goal

- Aligned messages/communication

Importance

- People to do the right thing to avoid risk

Coordinated Risk Communication – Terms of Reference

- Include communication experts from very beginning and throughout whole process/event from relevant agencies/organisations. Knowing who to contact (also in the press)
- Determine process when a coordinated risk communication is needed (checklist criteria)
- Knowing tasks and responsibilities of the involved organisations
- Establish and maintain communication channels in practice. Regular meetings with all kinds of stakeholders (building trust/relation)
- Think about how to use different tools e.g. social media
- Address concerns of the public – how? Describe possible process
- Develop approaches for different time scales (short term, long term) repeat the message later to change behavior
- Enforce a policy for handling sensitive information
- Define roles and responsibilities between agencies/organisations for each event
- Map of all stakeholders. Frequency of communications most important, all is too much
- Small event – big issue hitting the headlines
- Know in each other makes the information flow (also informal information) Align timing and content – arrange coordination. Every organisation has its own responsibility
- Define roles of responsibility for the participants
- Consider: it is a fixed group or a (partly) flexible group depending on the event
- Consider: arrange links to risk management group and/or risk assessment group
- Discuss how to make aligned communication with a group with own responsibilities
- How does the public perceive the problem?

Feasibility Assessment

Description

- Assessment of practicality of measures carried out by different person risk assessment/risk management/decision makers NOT DECISION MAKING!
 - Economic lost
 - Tech availability
 - Benefits
 - Proportionality
 - Acceptability stakeholders, cultural group
- } Engage stakeholders
(Iterative cycle)

Goal

- Increase prob. RA ends in success
- Risk assessment NOT influenced by feasibility

Feasibility Assessment – Terms of Reference

- See signal
- System not structure. Not too many groups (some people will be in all groups)
- Determine when the group comes together
- Determine whether this is a flexible group (with a core) or not
- Determine who decides to perform a feasibility assessment
- Determine the process when a feasibility assessment is done criteria/checklist)
- Determine roles: who is a decision maker, who is a consultant
- Discriminate between 'small' and 'big' measures (big measures broader stakeholder engagement)
- Consider determine when this discrimination is done as part of a risk assessment and when separately
- Take acceptability into account, next to (technical) feasibility, proportionality, cost-benefit etc.
- Set out non-partisan policy, to not be influenced by managers/assessors who try to 'push through' politically or economically motivated measures
- Set up a template of what feasibility assessment covers e.g. headings like: economic case, public safety case

Governance

Description/key words

- Determine legislation and stakeholders of structure/framework
 - Flexible for different events
 - Information management
 - Cultural awareness
- People that make the decision who is responsible for what?
- Organisation is different in different countries

Governance – Terms of Reference

- Define board or incorporated/part of another group
- Define legal framework and mandate
- Access cultural sensitivities
- Decide who is in charge within group (and collaborating partners). When it is risk managers at the administrative level from vet/med/food this is challenging
- Identify leader/decisionmaker in the One Health organisations/mother institutes and their mandate (also informal) and get to know them
- Write things down so when people exchange knowledge it is not lost – audit trail for data and decisions
- Multidisciplinary people or people from multiple disciplines?
- Regular meetings
- Determine decision making process (voting?) (when that is done in this group)
- Governance across different levels within organisations